

THE FINDING OF MEDITERRANEAN FRUIT FLY IN AUCKLAND, NEW ZEALAND AND THE MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE'S RESPONSE

Peter W Holder¹, Barney Stephenson¹ Kay Chadfield² and Ruth Frampton¹.

Late on May 2, 1996, two male fruit flies identified as Mediterranean fruit fly (*Ceratitis capitata* [Diptera: Tephritidae] or "medfly" for short), were collected from a trimedlure trap in Mt Roskill. This and subsequent medfly finds in the same immediate area has triggered a containment and eradication programme implemented by the Ministry of Agriculture.

Economically damaging tephritids attack sound ripe and ripening fruits. Medfly is a particularly serious horticultural pest due to its extremely wide host range (infests more than 250 fruit and vegetable species), broad eco-climatical tolerance, and rapid growth potential. The permanent establishment of medfly in New Zealand would also have trade implications for much of New Zealand's horticultural industry.

The initial flies were detected by the ongoing fruit fly surveillance programme. As a result of these captures, an A-zone of 200 metres radius and a B-zone of 1.5 kilometres radius were defined around the site of the finds.

Intensified surveillance

By the end of May 4, additional traps had been placed in both the A and B zones so that the distribution of the adult population could be defined. In the A-zone, 106 trimedlure traps and 47 protein hydrolysate bait traps have been hung in fruiting host trees, including at least one trimedlure trap on each of the 78 residential properties and 21 trimedlure traps in untended bush. In the B-zone, trimedlure traps have been hung at a density of between 20 - 30 traps km², giving a total of 231 B-zone traps.

Between May 2 and May 15, 41 adult medflies were caught. Nearly all were collected within five days of the response initiation. At the time of writing, there have been no adult catches since May 15.

Eggs and larvae are monitored by regular collections of ripe fruit from all preferred host plants in the A-zone. Sound fruit with no external sign of infestation are incubated at 26°C for a maximum of five days so that the almost invisible earliest life stages achieve detectable size. All fruit collected is dissected and examined for the presence of fruit fly immatures, and then destroyed immediately. Un-sound or suspicious looking fruit is not incubated but gets dissected etc straight away. The incubation, examination and destruction of fruit is done under strict and secure quarantine conditions (including barbed wire and burly guards)

Larval infestations have been detected in 12 pieces of fruit (feijoa, tangelo and grapefruit) from only five A-zone properties. These properties are also adjacent to the site of the initial adult finds. The last larval find was on May 23.

Eradication

As a result of adult flies being caught on May 5, spot spraying (no, not graffiti on Telecom dogs) of protein bait combined with maldison insecticide was initiated in the A and B zones. This involves the application of a minimum of one hundred 100-ml bait spots per hectare, with all host trees with fruit treated. Bait spot spraying is continuing

Cover and ground (directed at the soil inhabiting pupae) sprays are applied to any trees with infested fruit. In addition, all A-zone windfall host fruit is collected and destroyed weekly, or twice weekly at properties identified as those most likely to have larvae in fruit. Special care is taken not to remove all host fruit material, as host fruit deficiency is likely to encourage adults to disperse.

Other control efforts undertaken include preventing the movement of home grown host fruit from the A and B-zones, and ensuring fruit moving through the C-zone is insect proofed.

A co-ordinated team effort

The concurrent intensive sampling and control programmes as briefly described above have been carried out by closely co-ordinated specialised groups. We have achieved a great deal in a relatively short space of time and so far, the results of our efforts look promising. This has only been made possible thanks to capable and enthusiastic people, good leadership, and a carefully planned strategy based on sound technical decisions. It has been demanding and rewarding, and we'll still be here in the Spring!

¹New Zealand Plant Protection Centre, MAF Quality Management, Lincoln. ² MAF Regulatory Authority, Lincoln.

(well, spring has come and gone - Fortunately, the outbreak appears to have been contained)